

Final Voyage for an 1812 Era Gunboat Hull: Relocation of the Brown's Bay Vessel

Flora Davidson

Parks Canada, Conservation Services

1800 Walkley Road, Ottawa ON, Canada, K1A 0M5

The Brown's Bay Vessel was first brought to the attention of National Historic Sites Service by divers from the Kingston-Brockville area in 1966 (Zacharchuk, 1967). The wreck was found nestled in mud submerged under two meters of fresh water in an inlet of the St. Lawrence River at Brown's Bay, 50 km down river from Lake Ontario. The wreck was well known to local recreational divers and accounts of artifacts stamped with broad arrows having been removed from the site were reported. These reports prompted a test excavation at the site that summer because of the potential link of the vessel to the British Navy, who used the broad arrow marking to indicate their property.

It was during preliminary investigation that divers for the National Historic Sites Service reported a degree of disturbance to the sand covering on the wreck and that ship fittings, in particular copper fasteners, had been removed in such numbers that the bow planking had sprung loose (Zacharchuk, n.d.). The wooden hull, which measures approximately 16.5m in length with a span of 4.9m, did appear to be that of a British navy vessel, possibly a gunboat of the period 1788-1815 which were used during the War of 1812. The wreck, while large, is a relatively simple wooden hull with little remaining of the upper portion or decking. Examination of the hull revealed that while the vessel was likely built for the Royal Navy, it was later converted to a cargo vessel.

The War of 1812 was a significant event in the relations between Canada and the US. The war ended when the Treaty of Ghent was signed on Christmas Eve, 1814 which would mark the last armed conflict between the two neighbouring countries. During the war, both British and American gunboats patrolled the St. Lawrence, escorted convoys and transported troops. Finding an artifact potentially connected with this historically important period was enough to prompt a full archaeological excavation of the wreck. This was completed in just under two months in the late summer months of 1966. Shortly after this, the decision was made to raise it the following June.

After excavation, the wreck, still in the cradle used to raise it from the riverbed, was floated downstream to St. Lawrence Islands National Park in Mallorytown where it would be treated with polyethylene glycol (PEG). PEG treatment was still a relatively new process at the time and treating a hull of this size was ambitious, but would prove successful for the Brown's Bay Vessel. There, after treatment, it remained for the next forty years in an unheated boathouse built overtop of wood piling eight feet above the St. Lawrence River. While the conditions in the

boathouse were perhaps not ideal for preservation or interpretation, the hull remained in generally good condition with no signs of significant ongoing deterioration. However, there was plenty of room for improvement and the potential for deterioration was well noted over the decades in reports written by conservation, archaeology and interpretation officers at Parks Canada.

Brown's Bay Vessel being lowered into the treatment tank at Mallorytown Landing 1967 (Image: Parks Canada 6H4269T)

All assessments reached the same conclusion: the housing and display of the boat should be improved. Recommendations included improvement to:

- Heating/humidity control
- Physical support
- Lighting
- Access
- Housekeeping

The lack of heating, while identified as a potential problem for preservation and certainly limiting visitor access to the warmer months, was also cited in one report as a possible explanation of the absence of rapid drying that could otherwise have led to cracking during the cold dry winters at Mallorytown Landing (Murdock, 1985). Evaporation from the frozen river through floor vents may also have been a factor in this, but this would only be a very uneven source of humidity which might also have led to microclimates. Lighting in the boathouse was also poor. Natural light was limited for the most part and spot lights were used, though problematic, but in general recommended light levels were not exceeded. Limited interpretation of the vessel was available for the park visitors who ventured into the cramped quarters of the boathouse. Only parts of the starboard, bow and stern were visible from a small walkway around the boat and it was not at all evenly lit. The entire length of the port side was inaccessible and in darkness, out of view to visitors. The cradle used to support the hull further impeded views of the wreck. The cradle was, in fact, if anything overbuilt, unsightly and generally a detraction. Several detached pieces including the rudder, transom, stem fragment and crossbeams were

attached by iron wires and were not supported well or by approved conservation methods. If damage was to be averted over the long term, such deficiencies would have to be addressed.

The location and structure of the boathouse presented its own challenges too. It was difficult to prevent accumulations of dust and debris or to control pests such as insects and mice in such a remote and open structure. Furthermore, the building was not fitted with adequate barriers to vandalism or theft. The building also lacked sprinklers, fire alarms or a proper security system despite repeated recommendations for their installation.

The St. Lawrence Islands National Park is a destination for visitors who want to experience activities such as hiking, paddling, scuba, picnicking, swimming and wildlife: there seemed to be a mismatch between the Brown's Bay Vessel display and the outdoor experience which was the central theme of the park. Only limited portions of the park's budget and staff were available for the gunboat display and therefore very limited maintenance was carried out. The situation for the Brown's Bay Vessel continued to slowly deteriorate as the boathouse structure aged and the need for repairs mounted.

This leads to this latest chapter in the preservation and interpretation of this historic wreck. In August 2009, in preparation for the bicentennial commemorations of the War of 1812, it was announced that a 2 million dollar investment had been secured for visitor infrastructure at Fort Wellington National Historic Site, Prescott Ontario. The funds were part of the Canadian governments' Economic Action Plan to stimulate the economy during the global recession and were allocated to the building of a new visitor's reception centre to orient visitors to the significance of the site and its role in the War of 1812. Prescott, which is approximately 45km east of Mallorytown Landing, was also a good fit for the gunboat as it became an important naval staging area where gunboats were stationed throughout much of the war. By February 2011 a further 1.1 million was secured for an "enhanced 1812 themed exhibit for Fort Wellington National Historic Site ..[]which would feature a preserved British gunboat" (Parks Canada, 2010). It seemed, due to global hardship, that the Brown's Bay Vessel's luck was changing. There was just one outstanding issue: plans drawn up for the construction of the new Visitor Reception Centre and gunboat move were budgeted at 4 million dollars, almost 1 million over the funds available. Furthermore, the project would have to be completed within 2 years in order to receive the funding. Nevertheless, the decision was taken to proceed. A public opening of the not-yet-constructed Visitor Reception Centre with its central feature, the gunboat gallery, was set for May 2012 in time for the 200th commemoration of the War of 1812.

Challenges were many. For conservation it would include the logistics of moving the 16.5 meter 13 tonne hull 45 km by road to Fort Wellington and, once there, protecting it while the gallery was built around it from the ground up. The news of the project, however, was generally greeted as positive. The move would offer the chance to improve the exhibition, interpretation and preservation of the hull.

Fortunately, after years of reports and inspections, the overall condition of the Brown's Bay Vessel and the shortcomings of the display environment from both conservation and interpretation prospective were well studied. This gave a good basis to begin the process of designing the gallery at Fort Wellington. The project would be divided into several major areas: design and construction of the new Visitor's Centre with Gunboat Gallery, move of the Brown's Bay Vessel, completion of the gallery including replacement of the old cradle and cleaning of the boat. Success depended on co-ordinated efforts of many different groups including architects, engineers, site staff, construction workers, archaeologists, conservators and contractors all of whom would be working to a tight deadline.

Establishing timelines was essential to the completion of the project and used for charting work flow and coordinating events. When one event fell behind, the effect on the rest of the project was clearly noted and could be re-assessed. When construction fell behind on the finishing of the gunboat gallery, conservation had to re-assess and change its plans. Originally the boat was to be kept in the protective moving crate until construction of the gallery was complete. Unfortunately work on the gallery was too far behind to allow this and the crate had to be removed if construction of a new less cumbersome cradle for the boat and cleaning of the gunboat was to take place before the May 2012 opening. Opening the box and exposing the gunboat in what was still very much a construction zone was not a decision taken lightly. It would require extra vigilance on the part of all workers to keep to conservation approved work practices despite feeling the pressure of being behind schedule.

Conservation tasks were ordered on the timeline within a sequence of events. Timing of conservation activities was placed in relation to the progress that would have to be made in the construction of the new building. A pre-move assessment followed by securing and stabilizing the vessel to withstand the move occurred as ground was being broken on the site for the new construction. A Statement of Work for structural movers to move the vessel by road to the new site was drawn up by the project engineer in consultation with conservation. In this document details of the constructions and materials to be used to crate the boat for the move and to protect the boat while the gallery was constructed around it were outlined. The day of the move was to be a public event so the movers would also have to adhere to the requirements of a public event with media coverage. This would mean that the timing of the arrival at Prescott was important. The move would have to halt for the afternoon ceremony before the crated artefact could be lowered from the truck onto the exact position on the cement pad which was to be the floor of the gallery where the boat would be displayed. All such details were placed in the Statement of Work that went out with the tender.

Brown's Bay Vessel en route between Mallorytown Landing and Prescott, August 2011 (Image: Thierry Boyer, Parks Canada 6H4-2011-0949)

From the point of view of conservation, the most successful working relationships on this project with contractors were those that conservation was involved with right from the tendering process. It was easier to write specifics in the Statement of Work and explain the concerns before a contractor was hired to carry out the job than when a proposal had been already approved. Both the hiring of structural movers to crate, move and un-crate the Brown's Bay Vessel and the contractor hired to replace the old wooden cradle with a modern lightweight steel support were very satisfactory in this regard. Where conservation had not been closely involved with the tendering process, any adjustments made later meant additional negotiations and money had to be found to cover those expenses and, consequently, more time would be required. This was the case with the south facing curtain window wall in the gunboat which allowed a sweeping view of the fort and St.Lawrence River; visually striking and important for interpretation, but it allowed too much light to enter the gallery. Eventually this issue and others such as these were resolved, in this case by using both light filtering film and solar operated blinds.

Though the challenges in completing the project were many, the project was finished on time for the May 2012 opening. The Brown's Bay Vessel was a good fit to the site's main message "Fort Wellington Guardian of the St.Lawrence" and was well received by the public. The interpretation and visitor's experience of the gunboat was greatly increased and the move gave the opportunity to address conservation concerns which will allow future generations to appreciate what is the only known Royal Navy flat-bottomed boat surviving from the War of 1812 era. For Canadians, the preserved hull will continue to serve as a poignant reminder of a time when boats patrolled the northern shores of the St.Lawrence River against attack from the neighbours to the south.

Brown's Bay Vessel in the Gunboat Display at St. Lawrence Islands National Park, May 2010. (Image: Thierry Boyer, Parks Canada 6H40014EF)

Gunboat Gallery at the new Visitor Reception Centre, Fort Wellington National Historical Site, May 2012 (Image: Thierry Boyer, Parks Canada 6H40819EF)

Acknowledgments

Thanks must be given for the Government's "Canada Economic Action Plan" for providing the funds to carry out the project. The project involved numerous individuals, organizations and businesses. Many thanks to all of them including the architects, construction contractors and trades, and the Parks Canada team including site staff, interpretation officers, archaeologists, historians, engineers, conservators, communications and procurement specialists. Special thanks to Thierry Boyer, Elisabeth Pilon and Justin Bernard for their contributions to this presentation and to the volunteers on the project including students from the Algonquin College Applied Museum Studies programme who helped clean the gunboat; probably the largest artifact they will ever be called to vacuum and only one they'll be allowed to walk on!

*Student Volunteer at work cleaning, May 2012.
(Image: Thierry Boyer, Parks Canada 6H4-0767EF)*

Works Cited

Murdock, L. (1985). *Examination and Maintenance Recommendations for Brown's Bay Shipwreck on display at St. Lawrence Islands National Park Mallorytown, Ontario*. unpublished.

Parks Canada. (2010). *Government of Canada invests in tourism infrastructures at Fort Wellington National Historic Site of Canada*. Retrieved from Parks Canada: http://www.pc.gc.ca/apps/cp-nr/release_e.asp?id=1507&andor1=nr

Zacharchuk, W. (n.d.). *6H4-1967 Brown's Bay Excavation - Draft Report Original Notes*. unpublished.

Zacharchuk, W. (1967). The Raising of the Mallorytown Wreck. *The Conference on Historic Site Archaeology Papers*, (pp. 85-94).